

A concise study on Placement Management System

Alfiya Banu
MCA Scholar
School of CS and IT, Dept of MCA
Jain (Deemed-to-be University)-560069
Bangalore, Karnataka
Alfiyab38@gmail.com

Dr. Manju Bargavi S. K
Professor
School of CS and IT, Dept of MCA
Jain (Deemed-to-be University)-560069
Bangalore, India
bargaviskm@gmail.com

Abstract — The goal of the project is towards developing an application for the primarily web-based placement management system of a college. It is a web-based application designed in a windows platform for the placement department of the college in order to provide the details of its students in a database for the companies to their process of recruitment provided with proper login credentials. the system contains all the needed information about the students. the system stores all the personal information as well as their technical skills of the students that are required in the CV to be sent to a company. the colleges can utilize the system to manage student information with related to placement details. students should be able log in and upload their personal and Academic information, this project allows to keep track of student's information. It saves time by reducing manual work and using less paper work

Keywords: Authorization, Admin, Student, Management system, Web development.

I. Introduction

With so many placement activities going on around them, students in their final or third year of engineering college start to feel the pressure of the placement season. They want

to know where they stand and what they can do to improve their job prospects.

This is where the placement officer comes in handy. The admin provides crucial information to the students on how to prepare for the placement season. training and placement are a crucial aspect of every educational institution when the majority of the labour is still done by hand.

Every training and placement-related activity must be reported to the number of students by the training and placement officer.

A web application can be created to make the placement process easier and more successful for both the training and placement department and the students. this application creates a network of training and placement cells across the region, allowing every college and student to be notified if a placement-related activity occurs in one of their colleges. this approach can assist placement officers in providing information about new businesses.

Placement Management System is a web-based system to manage the placement process for students. The website was designed for students and faculty at institutions of higher education. It facilitates

the selection process of an institution, as well as providing academic support, information on policies and procedures, and other helpful resources.

According to multiple streams, and notify them whenever there is a change suited to the needs of the company officers in charge of placement provide student information and, if there are any modifications or additions, any student's profile must be updated on a regular basis. done by hand When it comes to this process, it's quite complex and time-consuming.

There's also the possibility of missing data. It's also tough to acquire, manage, and update student information. 'placement' becomes more important as the number of students rises. Students can see and evaluate their options. there will be several types of accounts admin, student, and HoD are examples of users.

For each student, the relevant credentials are created. the access point qualifying requirements imposed by the respective companies and a list of qualified candidates will be produced, and they will be interviewed. can decide whether or not they want to attend that particular event, test or drive

It provides a simple interface for the easy collation and maintenance of all manner of student information. The creation and management of accurate, up-to-date information regarding students' academic careers are critical for students and for the faculties.

Provides a variety of options for completing the task activities relating to the placement we use a modular-based system in this system.

Analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of students in order to make informed decisions about training and placement. depending on the query particular reports of the educational institute the pupils for the recruitment of various companies to investigate to do so, we'll use a variety of data mining algorithms. decisions that are based on a thorough grasp of the evidence are more effective. a web-based placement management solution that makes it easier to manage your placements students for a single assignment a registration system that reduces work on paper.

II. Literature Survey

The current placement cell methods and projects are time-consuming and difficult. Human involvement causes several analytical issues. Due to system flaws, these errors cause significant maintenance issues and student dropout. Manual labor makes documenting and categorizing extremely tough. These analytical techniques result in complicated administration and high analytical expenses, making the system costly and inefficient.

Human assistance is used in manual training and placement at various universities, which increases the chances of errors. The most serious issue is data on students is being searched and updated. placement officers are responsible for maintaining the student's profile as well as their records and documents. the placement officer is responsible for gathering the information. many companies that come for recruitment.

A final-year management system that offers all of the information on the students enrolled in the college. whereby we can overcome a variety of issues such as managing the thousands of student records and searching the list of students who meet

the criteria from among the tens of thousands of documents list companies that have visited the college for the aim of recruitment. recruiting students in order to automate the registration procedure and obtain a list of participants.

Students that are eligible for a college talent the system has been created. students that are eligible can apply. become a member of the portal and update their personal information. including their resume, which is accessible and seen by the public. director of placement the schedule is set by the placement officer. based on the institution's operations, In the end, the student will take place able to examine the results of the examination and the status of the case recruitment.

It concentrates on a user-friendly interface for updating student. in both universities and colleges, the creation and management of reliable, up-to-date information about a student's academic career is vital. student information systems deal with a variety of student information, academic reports, college information, course information, curriculum, batch information, placement information, and another resource.

It keeps track of all a student's information, which can be utilized for reporting, attendance monitoring, course progress, completed semesters, and years. Various reports and queries can be generated depending on a wide range of variables for students, batches, courses, teachers, exams, semesters, certification, and even the entire college as proposed in [1]

The placement cell coordinates a variety of placement activities for pupils. they had previously worked on separate domains but are now fast approaching each other. they provide industry-institute contact in this planned work.

The system's flaw is that the industry isn't directly linked to the pupils. It made use of the institute interaction interface as described in [2]

They conducted a study on in 2016. This project only allows for one-time registration. Companies are contacted by the placement cell to pick their pupils and view this résumé. disadvantages are a term used to describe the negative aspects of something. only email is used to send notifications as mentioned in [3]

They focus on providing a better way for staff and students to make the placement process less complicated and productive. the database and Linux server are used to construct this application. PHP will be used to link the database to the application. It is not always easy to access information stored on the server because the server may be down for a short period of time as explained in [4]

It primarily focusses on offering a straightforward interface for the collection and maintenance of all types of student data. it is vital for students, faculty, and administration at Sebha university in Libya, as well as any other educational institution, to create and manage accurate, up-to-date information about students' academic careers.

From enrollment until graduation, a student information system deals with a variety of data, including a program of study, attendance record, fee payment, and examination results, to name a few. All of this information must be accessible via an online interface as described in [5]

To improve the effectiveness of student management, it is necessary to have a student information management system in the face of a massive volume of data. standardized management, scientific

statistics, and quick queries of student information can all be accomplished with this system, reducing management workload. A typical student information management system will be developed in this study in order to achieve the systematization, standardization, and automation of student information as mentioned in [6]

It outlines the most efficient method of student placement. In this curriculum, the student is responsible for registering and discovering sources of information. How many students are there, and how many students have been placed for these graphs will be shown for the alumni student, a separate registration and profile will be created. Alumni are notified by default via email or text message. The company provides favorable conditions for pupils who are automatically qualified. the present student can examine and enter information, such as the registration plan for their CVs, which they can update on a regular basis. TPO has given student-organized information authorization to look for eligible students in accordance with business regulations and may send the eligible student a mail. TNP employees play a critical role in student accreditation and integration.

Set a schedule for online notifications and events, and find a student based on their external talents or activities. The corporation must obtain a register with information such as the URL, contact information, details, paper, and spaces. To manage the website, use a web server. TNP operational efficiency the website contains all of the information on the TNP program. SMS or the default email application is used to send notifications to each student as well as other software modules. A forum is a place where

people can chat with one another as proposed in [9]

This study explains how multiple tree decision algorithms are used to predict student placement performance. a decision algorithm for a tree, a decision-making structure in the shape of a tree. This system saves a lot of data while reducing people's efforts. the system focuses on training, cell placement, and profile matching automation. monitor and control the selection process' progress, and make contact with the most qualified person via SMS or email. They are the ones who come up with the rules for data classification as proposed in [8]

It is a web-based system. All students in the current batches of various streams can register their profiles using this system. Because the records were kept in modified access sheets, sorting issues arose. because the files were not saved in a hierarchical structure, a search problem arose as discussed in [9]

It is a web-based program designed on the Windows platform for the college's placement department in order to put the college's students' information in a database for firms to use in their recruitment process if they have a suitable login. all of the information about the students is stored in the system. the system saves all of the students' personal information as well as their technical skills, which are necessary for a CV that must be delivered to an employer. The system is an internet program that may be viewed both inside and outside the corporation with the right login credentials as mentioned in [10]

It is a technology that provides a quick placement management system in college, as opposed to the old system, which has a number of flaws that students and TPOs may

encounter, such as insufficient details, manual labor issues, and so on.

The placement management system website was created to address the shortcomings of previous placement systems. It allows end-users to register online using their CMSys (College Management System) account, which is a college website used to track attendance, term exam scores, and other information, browse and apply for companies of their choosing, and receive periodic placement updates from the college TPO. The college placement officers will not have to collect the information individually as described in [11]

It is a web-based program designed on the Windows platform for the college's placement department in order to put the college's students' information in a database for firms to use in their recruitment process if they have a suitable login. All of the information about the students is stored in the system. The system saves all of the students' personal information as well as their technical skills, which are necessary for a CV that must be delivered to an employer. The system is an internet program that may be viewed both inside and outside the corporation with the right login credentials the system can be used in a collegiate setting to manage student information related to placement this project includes all of the students' information.

Only the students can make changes to their personal information. Students can look for the information they need for the placement paper selection procedure.

All users can see what is going on at the college and what the students have accomplished as a result, our software provides a facility for preserving student information and retrieving the requested list of candidates for firms looking to hire employees based on a certain demand as proposed on [12]

III. Conclusion

In general, college placement administrators confront numerous challenges when it comes to manage student's information. It is more challenging because every information must be controlled so, there is a need to develop a web-based solution that can solve the discussed problem.

Compared to an existing computerized system, it performs at a faster pace. The system gives better feedback. Accurate information is available. It increases the systems and software's reliability by providing security.

Admin can view for which company student has applied for and accepted into and we believe that this project will be beneficial to many students in the future. As a result, we conclude that the proposed system will eliminate the existing systems flaws.

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